

EVALUATION OF CORROSIVE ENVIRONMENTAL
DEGRADATION OF GRP COMPOSITE USING
ACOUSTO-ULTRASONIC TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

The effect of acid environments on glass fibre reinforced plastic (GRP) composite is conducted in different concentrations of Sodium Chloride and Sulphuric Acid. The degradation in strength of GRP composite is evaluated by using acousto-ultrasonic technique of non-destructive testing. The results show that the percentage reduction in strength increases with increasing the immersion time of specimens in corrosive environments. However, the percentage reduction in strength of GRP composite can be related to the parameter known as "stress-wave-factor".

INTRODUCTION

The long-term performance of polymers and fibre-reinforced polymers matrix composite materials in aerospace applications depends on the stability of these materials under various environmental conditions. Glass fibre reinforced plastic (GRP) is extensively used in the chemical process industry for applications such as pipeline, pressure vessels and storage tanks. The conditions are often severe, frequently combining pressure, high temperatures and chemically reactive reagents. In most environments GRP is reasonably inert, especially when the component is not subjected to service loads.

Rege and Lakkad [1] have studied the effect of soaking in salt water and distilled water at various temperatures on the mechanical properties of glass fibre reinforced plastic and carbon fibre reinforced plastic composites. The results indicate that the degradation in compressive interlaminar and flexural strength is much more severe in salt water than in distilled water. The durability of stressed GRP in aqueous acidic environments has recently received considerable interest because of its long-term use in effluent pipes and chemical plant. Hogg and Hull [2] have demonstrated that environmental strain or stress corrosion cracking under conditions of constant deflection or constant load respectively, have essentially the same mechanism. Since it is now well established that these failures are characterized by planer fracture surfaces with little fibre pull-out, normal to the line of maximum stress. When the environment is acidic, this cracking can occur very rapidly and may result in catastrophic failure [3-4]. The degradation in strength of composite materials may result from chemical degradation of the matrix material, loss of strength of the reinforcing fibres by stress corrosion and accelerated degradation caused by combined action of temperature and chemical environment [5]. Retting et al. [6] have studied the corrosion mechanisms with the help of acoustic emission technique. Acoustic emission could also serve as a tool for new material inhibitor screening, process monitoring and upgrading of corrosion prone materials.

Evaluating the strength loss after use is particularly important in composite materials where moisture uptake and fatigue can cause strength to drop. Non-destructive evaluation (NDE) methods are needed, then, not only to find individually isolated defects, but also to find those things that are very subtle and distributed throughout the material. A new technique known as acousto-ultrasonic technique has get the capability to meet the aforementioned requirements [7]. Acousto-ultrasonic techniques is essentially an amalgamation of two separate existing techniques; acoustic emission and ultrasonics. In this acousto-ultrasonic technique; using an ultrasonic pulser, discrete ultrasonic pulses are injected into the material under test and the ultrasound is allowed to interact with the material. Due to this interaction of ultrasound with the internal features of the material (or say the microstructural environment within the material), the resultant wave form provides nothing but a modulated signal characterising the

material quality. An acoustic-emission sensor is then used to pick-up this resultant waveform (or the modulated signal of material quality). The acoustic emission signal thus obtained is then suitably processed and digitised to provide a measure of the quality of material under test. This measure is usually referred to an stress-wave-factor. The stress-wave-factor is arbitrary and depends on factors such as probe pressure, coupling, signal gain, reset-time, threshold voltage, repetition rate [8-9].

The ultrasonic waves input to the material under test is in the form of well defined discrete pulses. These ultrasonic waves are modulated/dampened differently by different materials and also by different features in the same material. A good quality material shall dampen the ultrasonic pulses to a lesser extent as compared to a material having gross distributed defects. The stress-wave-factor measurement, which is based on the oscillation counting of the resultant waveform, shall therefore be higher for good quality materials as compared to bad materials because, for the later case the resultant waveform is a highly dampened one. Defects such as misaligned and broken fibres, micro and macrovoids, resin crazing, cracks etc. all reduce the ability of fibre reinforced plastic (FRP) composites to propagate ultrasonic waves and hence the resultant waveform from a FRP composite containing these defects becomes a highly dampened one and the measured stress wave factor drop to a lower value for such composites [10]. In the work reported here, the effect of acid environments on GRP composite were studied by using acousto-ultrasonic technique of non-destructive testing and scanning electron microscopy method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Glass fibre reinforced plastic (GRP) samples were made with E-glass fibres and epoxy resin (CY-205 Araldite and HY-951 Hardner) by the hand lay-up method. The unidirectional GRP sheets produced by this means were 5 mm thick and 49 percent fibre volume fraction. Using these GRP sheets a number of tensile samples were cut for present study.

The instrumentation used for evaluating the ultimate performance of GRP samples before and after immersing in acids was acousto-ultrasonic apparatus (model, AET-206, AU). It is composed of three main sections- the pulser/ultrasonic section, sensor/acoustic emission section, and the display

section. Using a broad band transducer, the pulser injects ultrasonic pulses into the materials. The piezoelectric acoustic emission sensor probe having 375 KHZ resonant was used to received the transmitted stress wave. And broad band 40 DB preamplifier including a band pass filter frequency was matched to the AE sensor. The stress wave factor readings were noted for each GRP samples, when the noise interference was minimum, and good contact between the AET probe and surface of the sample using petroleum jelly as a couplant. Also, press the sensor fixture firmly against the samples. This will reduce the chance of erroneous acoustic signals emanating from the fixture itself or from friction noises caused by the sensor sliding over the samples. The schematic diagram of the stress wave factor measurements are shown in figure 1. Each GRP sample having different stress wave factor were marked by dye-pen for corrosive environmental testing in different concentration of sodium chloride and sulphuric acid.

Figure 1. Diagram of Apparatus for measurement of stress wave factor.

These samples were immersed in different concentration of Sodium Chloride (60%, 40% and 20%) and Sulphuric Acid (60%, 40% and 20%) for the study of corrosive environments. At an interval of every four days, one sample each were removed from each of the chemical solutions mentioned above. These samples were then used for acousto-ultrasonic testing

and ultimate tensile testing. Fractured samples were mounted on stubs with the help of silver paste. Photomicrographs were obtained using polaroid camera back attached to the oscilloscope on an PSEM-500 scanning electron microscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The values of percentage reduction of glass fibre reinforced plastic composite in acid environments, calculated from the initial and degraded values. The percentage reduction in tensile strength of GRP composite in different concentration of Sulphuric Acid (60%, 40% and 20%) and Sodium Chloride (60%, 40% and 20%) are illustrated in figure 2.

Figure 2. Percentage reduction in tensile strength increases with immersion time of GRP samples.

The results show that the percentage reduction in tensile strength increases with increasing the immersion time. The reduction in tensile strength of GRP samples occur when diffusing molecules of chemicals rupture the intermolecular bond in the epoxy resin and at the interface [11]. The GRP composites are also absorb water uptake from the diluted acids, which due to capillary conduction along the fibres, an effect known as 'Wicking'. The effect of acids on GRP samples are saturated after 24 to 28 days. It is also important to note that the rate of Sulphuric Acid diffusion through epoxy resin is more than the Sodium Chloride. Therefore,

the percentage reduction in tensile strength of GRP composites in Sulphuric Acid is more than the Sodium Chloride. However, the value of stress wave factors have tried to evaluate the percentage reduction in ultimate performance of GRP composite in acid environments and this is illustrated in figure 3.

Figure 3. Percentage reduction in stress wave factor increases with immersion time of GRP samples.

It can be seen that the percentage reduction in stress wave factor also increases with increasing immersion time. It is reasonable to conclude that the percentage reduction in tensile strength increases with increasing percentage reduction in stress wave factor as shown in figure 4.

The lower values of stress wave factor (or say maximum percentage reduction in stress wave factor) indicates that the GRP samples have been extensively corroded with acids. Vary and Lark [9] have studied that stress wave factor is a sensitive indicator of composite strength variation that accompany various type of failures. The working hypothesis is that attenuated stress wave energy flow corresponds to decreased fracture resistance. Apparently, the stress wave factor provides a means of rating of efficiency of dynamic strain energy transfer in a GRP composite material. Our view of the results is that a GRP composite material that is more efficient in transfer of stress wave energy will exhibit greater strength (or say minimum percentage reduction in tensile strength in acid environments).

Figure 4. Relation between percentage reduction in tensile strength with percentage reduction in stress wave factor of GRP composite.

(a)

(100μm)

(b)

(100μm)

Figure 5. Photomicrograph showing effect of immersion of GRP samples in Sodium Chloride.

SEM (Scanning electron micrograph) photomicrograph 5(a) and 6(a) showing the effect of immersion of GRP samples in Sulphuric Acid and Sodium Chloride. The initiation of pit occurs on a GRP surface due to

(a)

(100 μ m)

(b)

(10 μ m)

Figure 6. Photomicrograph showing effect of immersion of GRP samples in Sulphuric Acid.

an increase in the rate of acid diffusion through the resin. The crack propagated in a plane parallel to the fibres at or near to the fibre-resin interface. The Sulphuric Acid is corroded on the surface of the epoxy resin as shown in figure 5(b). The epoxy resin depicts a cleavage type failure as shown in figure 5(b) and 6(b). There appears to be a strong interface between the fibre and epoxy resin. Thus fractographic studies show that the acidic environments can cause the degradation in ultimate performance of the GRP composites.

CONCLUSIONS

The glass fibre reinforced plastic composite is susceptible to rapid corrosion in acid environments because, of the loss of integrity of the fibre/resin interface. However, the degradation in ultimate performance of GRP composite in acid environments can be easily evaluated by the value of stress wave factor.

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